

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

NEUTRALIZATION OF HALOGEN-CONTAINING WASTE GASES OF THE ISOTOPE SEPARATION PLANT TO THE SANITARY STANDARDS LEVEL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8005192>

Abstract

Tests have been carried out, giving the basis for the modernization of gas and dust collection installation of the plant using a highly effective chemical absorber such as modernized mercerized wood. The Isotope Separation Plant (ISP) of OJSC Siberian Chemical Combine became ecologically safe on gas emissions, as the content of fluorides and chlorides immediately after the installation (before dilution with atmospheric air) does not exceed sanitary standards, equal to 0.5 mg/m^3 and 1.0 mg/m^3 respectively. For the first time ever purification of exhaust gases was achieved at a level below the maximum allowable concentration, instead of the technically normative level, which is set for each industrial enterprise.

Keywords: chemical absorber, exhaust gas purification, volatile fluorides and chlorides, hydrogen fluoride, maximum allowable concentration.

Introduction

For a long time, a gas-dust-trapping unit (GDTU), designed for neutralization of gas mixtures based on fluorine, chlorine trifluoride and its decomposition products, has existed at ISP (Isotope Separation Plant). As an absorber, they used waste from a quarry producing marble, the so-called marble crumb with particle sizes from 1 to 5 cm. When the task of reduction of harmful emission into the atmosphere was set, as a part of State Corporation Rosatom ecological program, there was a need to find more effective absorbers than marble crumbs for fluorine and chlorine containing gases. During research when choosing alternative absorbers, for example, ChAL (Chemical absorber lime), alumina gel, ChAS (Chemical absorber soda), it was proved that all of them do not meet the requirements on neutralization of waste halogen-containing gases, as well as marble crumbs, which is caused by insufficient degree of purification from halogen-containing substances due to products of chlorine trifluoride interaction with deposits on the equipment having a small chemical activity. At other sections of ISP, for example, at collectors of instrumentation, a wood-based chemical absorber, ChA-MW, was successfully used for complete capture of hydrogen fluoride. In some cases, in the presence of elemental fluorine and chlorine

trifluoride in the gases, modernized mercerized wood (ChA-MMW) was used. Technical normative emission of Isotope Separation Plant of OJSC Siberian Chemical Combine is 3 mg HF/m^3 . In wooden absorbers, the main absorbing reagent NaOH is chemically more active with respect to acid gases than Ca(OH)_2 , which is the basis of the lime absorber (ChAL), and even more being compared with the crystalline CaCO_3 - the base of the marble crumbs. Besides, in a lime absorber there is no reducing additive, and in the modernized mercerized wood it is Na_2SO_3 by means of which relatively inert compound Cl_2 is reduced to HCl and more actively interacts with sodium alkali [1, 2]. Thus, testing of ChA-MMW in the conditions of GDTU operation, as the last sanitary stage of decontamination of exhaust gas mixtures containing fluorine, chlorine trifluoride and its decomposition products, became an urgent necessity to ensure environmental friendliness of the plant.

Thermodynamic calculations have confirmed that alkali metal hydroxides are the most chemically active with respect to acid substances in comparison with active compounds of other absorbents (Table 1). The changes of Gibbs energy were calculated for the reactions of the absorbent active component with HF.

Table 1.

Change of standard Gibbs energy

Absorbent	Active ingredient	$-\Delta G_{298}^0$, kJ/g-mol	$-\Delta G_{298}^0$, kJ/g- equivalent
ChA-MMW ChAL	NaOH	939,4	939,4
Alumina gel ChAMg	Ca(OH) ₂	852,7	426,4
ChAS	Al ₂ O ₃	641,1	320,5
ChA-MS	Mg(OH) ₂	637,3	318,6
	Na ₂ CO ₃	434,1	217,0
	CaCO ₃	328,5	164,2

Halogen-containing gases are neutralized at the GDTU before release into the atmosphere. For accumulation and supply of mixtures to the unit, a system of gas collection into receivers with a total volume of more than 500 m³ and a multistage compressor unit are installed. All receivers can be used to store fluorine and chlorine trifluoride of any concentration. The maximum pressure in the receivers does not exceed 93.4 kPa. Halogen-containing gases are discharged through the unit periodically 1 to 3 times a month during 2 to 10 hours through a 50 m high pipe diluted with air at a ratio of 1:(500 - 800).

Materials and methods

A schematic process flowchart of the GDTU is presented in the figure 1. While testing absorbing efficiency of absorbers the first three absorbing columns 3, 4 and 5 were filled with 900 kg of marble crumbs each, column 6 - with 500 kg of lime absorbent, the last one - with 400 kg of modernized mercerized wood with

forced compaction of layers up to 0.35-0.40 g/cm³, at the outlet of the column a layer of marble crumbs was placed, which plays the role of a bulk filter and a passive press.

Before the absorbing columns with marble crumbs, two parallel columns of the volume of 150 l each there were placed with the granulated sorbent NaF of the total mass of 200 kg, to prevent the contamination of the absorbers by uranium, and also to decrease substantially the HF and SiF₄ content in the mixture. Absorption of these components occurs through the reactions

It should be noted that sodium fluoride does not interact with elemental fluorine and fluorohalides such as ClF₃, ClF, as well as with sulfur fluorides.

Fig. 1. Schematic apparatus diagram of gas-dust collecting unit. 1, 2, 9 - standard sampling devices; 3 - 5 - absorption columns with marble crumbs; 6 - absorption column with lime absorbent; 7 - absorption column with modernized mercerized wood; 8 - exhaust pipe; 10 - sorption column with NaF; 11 - air fan.

The research methodology consisted in consecutive passing of gases through a cascade of absorbers with sampling after each type of chemical absorbers, as well as the initial gas mixture coming to the columns with sodium fluoride. Gas samples were taken into standard 6-liter reservoirs, pre-washed with nitrogen and evacuated to a pressure of no more than 26 P. After that, these vessels were fulfilled with sample gas up to pressure no more than 66.7 kPa, and analyzed using a mass-spectrometer МИ-1201АГМ-02 (Russia) and a Perkin-Elmer "Spectrum GX" (USA) infrared spectrophotometer. In case of small content of fluorine in a sample, for its quantitative definition was used a

method of reverse potentiometric titration with the use of ion-selective LaF₃-electrode by the method, described in work [4], the essence of which consists in adding to an aliquot of isopropanol or acetone in ratio 1:(2-5).

The following substances were used in tests: sodium fluoride (NaF) - cylindrical granules of 6mm x 6mm size (RU TU 002. 65-83); marble crumbs - crystalline calcium carbonate with a grain of any shape and size from 10 to 25 mm (RU GOST 2286); lime chemical absorbent granulated, containing 96% by mass of Ca(OH)₂ and 4% by mass of NaOH (RU GOST 6765); modernized mercerized wood (Fig. 2) [2].

Fig. 2. Types of mercerized wood [3]

Results and discussion

During the tests 154 m³ of gas mixtures containing chlorine trifluoride and its decomposition products was passed through the unit. The total mass of fluorine and chlorine in the components of gas mixture was 151.5

kg and 83.7 kg respectively. Volumes of gases which were subsequently supplied at the absorption stage (V_{in}), and the final volume of vented gases (V_{end}) before their dilution with atmospheric air are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Gas volume change, m³

Emission number	Source	After sodium fluoride	After marble crumbs	After lime absorber	Final, after ChA-MMW	V_{in}/V_{end}
1	22	18.5	30.3	18.3	17.0	0.77
2	28	25.8	43.0	22.2	19.8	0.71
3	32	28.2	43.2	28.0	24.4	0.76
4	27	24.6	27.8	21.2	18.6	0.69
5	25	23.9	33.2	26.3	19.4	0.78
6	20	17	21.3	16.4	14.3	0.72
Σ	154	138	198.8	132.4	113.5	0.74

Reduction of the volume of emitted gases by more than a quarter in average is caused by a more complete absorption of halogen-containing components of gas mixtures and significant reduction in the volume of CO₂ formed in the interaction of components with CaCO₃ and captured at the following stages by Ca(OH)₂ and NaOH.

As follows from Table 3, the application of modernized mercerized wood at the last treatment stage leads to almost complete absorption of halogen fluorides and elemental halogens and some fluorides, which are trapped insufficiently in marble crumbs and lime absorbent. The content of ClF₃, ClF, ClO₂F, F₂ and UF₆ in the gas stream decreases from stage to stage. If in the initial three or four emissions the content of these components decreases significantly after they pass through the marble aggregate, in the subsequent ones their presence is recorded after the lime absorber. This can serve

as a signal of the exhaustion of the resource of absorbers on the previous stages.

However, the Cl₂ concentration in the gas flow can be a more significant criterion of the resource exhaustion of the absorbers of the trapping unit. The average degree of Cl₂ absorption (for six emissions) is 98.5%, reaching in the first four emissions ~100%, in the fifth - 99.5%, in the sixth - only 93.2%. The similar picture was observed when capturing HF. In the initial five emissions HF absorption is complete, in the sixth - 99.4%.

Thus, the HF and Cl₂ content in the passing gas can be a resource criterion for each stage of the unit. In this case the Cl₂ detection after the last stage with modernized mercerized wood is the criterion of depletion of the resource of all chemical absorbers of the unit without exclusion.

Table 3.

Component composition of halogenide gases with the account of the volume change (change of nitrogen and oxygen contents is not shown), % by volume

Component	Sampling point of mixture*	Emission number						Average absorption degree, %
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
ClF ₃	Source	23.2	31.0	23.8	0**	30.2	30.5	100
	P-1	27.8	33.6	27.1	0	32.1	32.0	
	P-2	0	0.5	0.7	0	7.2	5.2	
	P-3	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.3	
	End	0	0	0	0	0	0	
ClF	Source	7.4	14.5	11.4	14.2	12.5	14.4	100
	P-1	8.8	15.7	12.4	14.9	13.1	14.6	
	P-2	0.1	0.5	0	0	0.9	2.8	
	P-3	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.2	
	End	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cl ₂	Source	4.8	5.0	1.5	10.2	5.6	4.4	>98.5
	P-1	5.7	5.4	1.7	11.0	5.6	4.5	
	P-2	0.3	7.2	3.0	4.7	8.7	22.1	
	P-3	0	3.5	2.1	2.8	5.3	6.1	
	End	0	0	<0.1	0	<0.1	0.3	
F ₂	Source	0	0.5	0.2	2.5	0	0.1	100
	P-1	0	0.5	0.2	2.8	0	0.1	
	P-2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.1	
	P-3	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	End	0	0	0	0	0	0	
HF	Source	18.0	8.5	12.9	10.0	5.0	16.8	>99.8
	P-1	2.0	1.7	1.4	1.5	0.7	2.8	
	P-2	0.4	3.2	2.0	1.8	0.7	4.8	
	P-3	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	
	End	0	0	0	0	0	<0.1	
CO ₂	Source	0	1.2	1.0	0	1.0	1.2	Displacement of CO ₂ from CaCO ₃ and absorption on Ca(OH) ₂ and NaOH
	P-1	0	1.3	1.5	0	1.2	1.3	
	P-2	43.2	46.7	39.4	23.4	32.8	21.6	
	P-3	7.6	11.3	12.9	6.1	20.5	14.0	
	End	0	0.6	0.6	0.2	1.7	8.4	
UF ₆	Source	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0	0.1	100
	P-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	End	0	0	0	0	0	0	

* - after each type of absorbent: NaF (P-1), marble crumbs (P-2), lime absorbent (P-3), modernized mercerized wood (Final)

** - below detection limit.

It should be noted that sodium fluoride is not a chemical scavenger (C), but a sorbent (S). The difference is that some absorbed components of gas mixtures, such as HF, can be reversibly extracted from the sorbent, and the sorbent can be used repeatedly.

In contrast to sorbents, the chemical scavenger binds fluorides by chemical transformation of the scavenger base with release of non-fluoride compounds into the gas phase (G)

Thus, the advantage of the sorbent in comparison with a chemical scavenger is that the sorbent can be

used repeatedly. The disadvantage of the sorbent is selective absorption of gas components. In its turn, the advantage of a chemical scavenger is that with its power it is possible to capture almost all active components of gases, but only once [5].

Regeneration of NaF is carried out at 175 - 200°C, desorbing at first HF, then at 350 - 400°C uranium hexafluoride [6].

Note also that the main amount of SiF₄ is captured by NaF, which leads to "poisoning" of the sorbent. The working capacity of sodium fluoride decreases. This is due to the fact that the decomposition temperature of Na₂SiF₆ according to different authors is 615 - 700° C. At such temperature NaF becomes sintered, losing its sorption characteristics, and becomes unsuitable for further removal of HF and UF₆ [6].

In addition, we must say, that by the moment of almost complete loss of resource of a marble crumbs

and lime absorber at the next emission it is necessary to reduce the gas flow rate approximately by 1.5 times due to formation of large quantity of CO₂ and O₂ due to which the gas volume increases by 30% - 40% and accordingly, the speed of its passage through the unit increases. In addition, the gas flow through the layer of modernized mercerized wood cannot exceed 0.5 l/(cm²·min) or 78 m³/(m²·h) [3]. At a flow rate of initial gas of 20 m³/h or 77 m³/(m²·h) with a cross-sectional area of the absorption column of 0.26 m² an increase in flow rate by 1.5 times will lead to violation of the integrity of this layer.

Data in Table 4 shows that fluoride content along the height of the marble-crumb layer in all the columns is almost the same which testifies to complete depletion of working capacity. In its turn the chloride content is

minimum, which means complete displacement of chlorine from formed calcium chloride by fluorine in the reaction

Despite the small working capacity, almost 65% of the incoming fluorine in the form of various fluorine-containing compounds is extracted in the marble. But the displaced chlorine, usually in the chemical form Cl₂, goes to the lime absorber and upgraded mercerized wood. The content of fluorine ion and chlorine ion in the lime absorber is comparable. It can be explained by the fact that Ca(OH)₂ reacts well with both fluorine- and chlorine-containing compounds, but the first components in gas entering the lime-absorbent unit are smaller than in the initial mixture, and therefore the processes of chlorine displacement are less intensive.

Table 4.

Composition of exhaust absorbers

Sorbent	Fluorine content		Chlorine content	
	%	кг	%	кг
Sodium fluoride	7.0	14.1	0	0
Marble crumbs (1st column)	3.9	35.1	0	0
Marble crumbs (2nd column)	3.6	32.4	0.06	0.5
Marble crumbs (3rd column)	3.8	34.2	0.02	0.2
Lime absorber	4.2	20.9	6.5	32.7
MMW	4.9	14.7	16.5	49.5

However, part of the Cl₂ displaced at this stage passes the lime absorber and is completely captured on the upgraded mercerized wood. In addition, at the last stage the residual number of fluorine-containing components is neutralized. The nature of halogenide distribution over the layer height of both absorbers - the presence of fluorine-ion and absence of chlorine-ion in the inlet layer and the opposite picture in the outlet layer - proves that upon combined absorption of fluorine and chlorine containing compounds chlorine displacement from the resulting chloride salts is observed.

The distribution of halides in the absorbers proves that the filtering installation life depends only on the operating time of modernized mercerized wood. At the same time, the slippage of harmful chemicals occurs only after the last absorbent layer is completely worked off. Unfortunately, it is intrinsic negative feature, as it makes it difficult to define the exact lifetime based on the outlet gas composition. It is possible to estimate the time of protective action of the modernized mercerized wood layer according to Shilov-Dubin equation, which parameters for mercerized wood being almost its full analogue were obtained when absorbing HF

$$\theta_{\text{HF}} = \frac{8,13}{GC^{0,87}} \left[L - 0,18dG^{0,1} (\lg C_o + 2,46) \right]$$

where θ_{HF} - time of protective action of an absorber layer, min; G - gas flow rate, l/cm²·min; C_o - initial HF content, mMol/l; L - height of an absorber layer, cm; d - determining grain size of an absorber, cm (for these absorbers d = 0.05 - 0.1 cm) [7].

In addition, the degree of ChA-MMW depletion can be determined by a change in its chromaticity in accordance with the work [8].

Analysis has shown that during the whole period of testing fluoride content in the purified gas mixtures

did not exceed 0.3 mg/m³ and chloride content - did not exceed 0.5 mg/m³, which is significantly below not only the technical normative emissions, but also below the maximum allowable concentrations of fluorine and chlorine in the working area.

Thus, the unit completed with 200 kg of NaF sorbent, 2 ton of marble crumbs, 500 kg of lime absorbent and 400 kg of modernized mercerized wood results in purification of high concentrated gases containing 200 - 250 kg of halogen containing compounds to permissible sanitary norms. In order to increase the resource of purification of gases containing up to 350 - 400 kg of halogen-containing compounds at the present time columns No2 and No3 are fed with 500 kg of lime absorbent each instead of marble crumbs. The average collection efficiency is 99.7% and 98.5% for fluorine- and chlorine-containing components correspondingly.

Based on the results of this and earlier studies, an estimation of surface concentrations of HF and Cl₂ within the aerodynamic shade of the building, where the GDTU is located, was made for five tested schemes by the procedure [9]: I - five columns with marble crumbs; II - NaF → three columns with marble crumbs → two columns with lime absorber; III - NaF → two columns with lime absorber → three columns with marble crumbs; IV - NaF → three columns with marble crumbs → column with lime absorber → column with modernized mercerized wood; V - NaF → column with marble crumbs → three columns with lime absorber → column with modernized mercerized wood. After installation, the gases were diluted with air at a ratio of 1:500, which are discharged into the atmosphere through an exhaust pipe 50 m high.

Schemes IV and V do not practically differ in their absorption characteristics, as in any case the criterion for working out of the schemes as a whole will be the

column resource with modernized mercerized wood. The difference is 1.5 times higher gas mixtures processing according to scheme V due to more significant

working capacity of lime absorbent as compared with marble crumbs (Table 5).

Table 5.

Results of neutralization of waste gases

Scheme	Mass of fluorine, kg		Degree absorption, %	Mass of chlorine, kg		Degree absorption, %
	served	caught		served	caught	
I	64.4	58.5	90.6	73.2	49.8	43.8
II	65.5	62.3	95.1	79.4	68.3	80.9
III	30.9	27.8	90.0	93.6	38.3	31.7
IV	151.5	151.4	99.9	83.7	82.7	98.5
V	215.2	215.1	>99.9	114.5	113.2	98.5

As can be seen in Table 6, the HF concentration within the aerodynamic shade of the building is below Maximum allowable concentration for the work area (MAC_{wa}) for all studied schemes.

Table 6.

Ground concentration of HF

Scheme	Contents HF ([HF]), mg/m ³	Ratio content (R*)
I	0.38	0.76
II	0.17	0.34
III	0.10	0.20
IV, V	0.009	0.02

* $R = [HF] / (MAC_{wa})_{HF}$, where $(MAC_{wa})_{HF} = 0,5 \text{ mg/m}^3$

In terms of chlorine content, purification by schemes IV and V is the most effective (Table 7).

Table 7.

Surface concentration of Cl₂

Cxema	Contents of Cl ₂ (C ₀), mg/m ³	Ratio of content (R*)
I	1.96	1.96
II	0.77	0.77
III	1.92	1.92
IV, V	0.015	0.015

* $R = [Cl_2] / (MAC_{wa})_{Cl_2}$, where $(MAC_{wa})_{Cl_2} = 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$

When using mainly marble crumbs, chlorine emissions are higher than the permissible ones. It should be noted that schemes IV and V are 10-15 times more effective than other schemes in neutralization of fluorine-containing components and 50 times more effective in capturing chlorine-containing compounds in exhaust gases.

Conclusion

Scheme IV is used as the main scheme of neutralization of waste halogen-containing gases at the ISP because of the relative scarcity of ChA-MMW. At present, gas emission through the plant is carried out solely on the production need at any time of the day, regardless of wind direction and weather conditions, without accumulating significant amounts of highly toxic chemically active compounds.

Modernization of the gas-dust separation plant with the use of a highly efficient chemical absorber of modernized mercerized wood type together with a lime absorber has led to the fact that the Isotope Separation Plant of Siberian Chemical Complex became environmentally safe in terms of gas emissions, since the content of fluorides and chlorides immediately after the plant (before dilution with atmospheric air!) as a rule does not exceed sanitary norms set by the Russian Federation law.

It is important to note that for the first time ever emission purification was achieved at the Maximum

Allowable Concentrations level and not at the technically normative level set individually for every industrial enterprise.

Equipping the enterprises of the nuclear fuel cycle with such systems for neutralization of exhaust gases will make it possible to reduce considerably the environmental pollution.

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the personnel of Isotope Separation Plant of OJSC Siberian Chemical Combine S.A. Ilyin, Yu.B. Torgunakov, E.V. Martynov, I.M. Dmitriev, P.V. Zernayev, V.V. Gorin for fruitful scientific discussions and valuable recommendations which undoubtedly improved the contents of this paper.

References:

- Gromov O.B. Processing and Utilization of Uranium- and Fluorine-Bearing Gas Mixtures of Separation Production // Chemical Technology, 2009, vol. 10, No 3, p. 183.
- Patent No 2283176 RU Chemical absorbent for neutralization of halogen-containing and acid gases and a method for its preparation // V.V. Vodolazskikh, O.B. Gromov, B.M. Zimin et al. Bulletin "Inventions. The useful models", 2006, No 25, p. 47.
- Gromov O.B. A Research and Development of the Technology of Wood-Based Chemical Absorbents

for Neutralization of the Fluorinated Gases of the Separation Production // Ph.D. candidate of technical sciences, JSC "VNIHT", 2009, 202 p.

4. USSR Author's certificate No 1762229 Method for Determination of REE and/or Yttrium Ions or Their Sum // O.B. Gromov. Bulletin. "Inventions", 1992, No 26, p. 6.

5. Gromov O.B., Scherbakov V.I., Evdokimov A.N., et al. Chemical absorbers for capturing gaseous fluorides at low pressures // Chemical Technology, 2004, No 10, p. 27.

6. Galkin N.P., Zaitsev V.A. & Seregin M.B. Capture and Processing of Fluorine Gases. Moscow: Atomizdat, 1975, 240 p.

7. Gromov O.B Chemisorption of Hydrogen Fluoride in a Stationary Layer of a Chemical Absorbent under Dynamic Conditions // Chemical Technology, 2010, vol. 11, No 6, p. 360.

8. Patent No 2459204 RU Method of Sorbent State Diagnostics // Gromov O.B., Dyachenko A.N., Zernaev P.V., et al. Op. 20.08.2012. Bulletin. "Inventions", 2012, No 23, p. 12.

9. Tishchenko N.F. Protection of Atmospheric Air. Calculation of harmful substances and their distribution in the air. Reference book. Moscow: Chemistry, 1991, 376 p.